

The Challenges for Regulating Medical Use of ChatGPT and Other Large Language Models

By Timo Minssen LL.D., Effy Vayena PhD, I. Glenn Cohen JD

Timo Minssen LL.D., Professor of Law, University of Copenhagen (UCPH, DK), Founding Director of UCPH's Center for Advanced Studies in Biomedical Innovation Law (CeBIL), Research Affiliate at LML, University of Cambridge, UK.

Effy Vayena PhD, Professor of Bioethics at the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology (ETHZ, CH), Deputy head of the Institute of Translational Medicine.

I. Glenn Cohen JD, Deputy Dean and James A. Attwood and Leslie Williams Professor of Law, Harvard Law School, Faculty Director, Petrie-Flom Center for Health Law Policy, Biotechnology, and Bioethics, Harvard University, Cambridge, MA.

Corresponding Author: I. Glenn Cohen JD, Deputy Dean and James A. Attwood and Leslie Williams Professor of Law, Harvard Law School, Faculty Director, Petrie-Flom Center for Health Law Policy, Biotechnology, and Bioethics, Harvard University, Cambridge, MA. 1525 Massachusetts Ave, Griswold Hall 503, Cambridge MA 02138. lgcohen@law.harvard.edu

Disclosures: Professor Cohen is a member of the ethics advisory board for Illumina and the Bayer Bioethics Council. Professor Vayena is a member of IQVIA's ethics advisory panel and a member of Merck KGaA digital ethics advisory panel. Professor Minssen provides legal advice to Corti, and is a member of the IP Advisory Board for Christian Hansen A/S. He also gave comments on the WHO's "AI for Health Legislation Policy Brief". Professor Vayena and Minssen served in the external WHO expert group on the Ethics and Governance of Artificial Intelligence for Health and serve on the external WHO expert group on Ethical Considerations for the Use of Large Multi-Modal Models for Health-Related Applications.

Funding/Support: Cohen and Minssen's work is supported by a Novo Nordisk Foundation-grant for a scientifically independent Collaborative Research Programme in Biomedical Innovation Law (grant agreement number NNF17SA0027784). Timo Minssen's work for this contribution was further supported by the CLASSICA Project on AI-assisted cancer surgery funded by the European Union (Grant Agreement no. 101057321). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Effy Vayena's work is partly supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation Grant NRP77, award Number #407740_187356/1.

Word Count: 1272

The introduction of artificial intelligence (AI) into medical devices, decision support, and clinical practice is not new, with a particular uptick in investment and deployment in the last decade. Regulators (e.g., FDA, EMA, and CFDA), intergovernmental organizations (e.g. WHO), civil society groups, institutional review boards at hospitals, and others have worked hard to define the scope of what applications should require review and approval, implementing rules in a fast-changing terrain with mixed results. What has changed is the public availability and interest in large language models (LLMs), most notably Open AI's ChatGPT and Google's Bard, with potential applications to medicine. These models are large (1 trillion parameters for GPT-4 and growing), general rather than trained for a specific task (though finetuning is possible), autoregressive (using only past values to predict future ones) and foundational (likely to be the seed for many further devices and applications).¹ There has also been interest in creating LLMs with more curated medical training data, such as Google's Med-PaLM2. The medical world has taken note, with a wide range of use cases from generating draft progress plans, to answering patient medical questions via a chatbot.² In this Viewpoint, we discuss how regulators across the world should approach the legal and ethical challenges raised by medical use of LLMs, including: privacy, device regulation, competition, intellectual property rights, cybersecurity, and liability.

Privacy: LLMs are trained on vast amounts of data scraped from the web and other digital sources, that may contain personal data. In the EU, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) permits access to personal data, including health data, only with specific justifications (e.g. informed consent or public interest). OpenAI's ChatGPT is currently under investigation by European national authorities in order to assess compliance with the GDPR.³ A different privacy problem may occur in the U.S. under the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act of 1996 (HIPAA), or state privacy laws, if physicians include protected patient data in prompts they submit to LLMs. The more general ethical questions that regulators need to grapple with is: when are LLM's scraping of patient data from the web or other data sets permissible and whether patients should be able to opt out of such uses? An important first step would be for privacy regulators in the U.S., the EU, and elsewhere to issue specific guidance, binding or advisory, as to privacy permissible and impermissible ways to develop and deploy LLMs. Harmonization between these regulators is also an important next step to the extent possible.

Device Regulation: Under U.S. and EU law LLM software that is only developed for general purposes and without any claims to their use for medical purpose would usually not qualify as medical devices. However, LLMs that are developed, modified or directed to specific medical purposes, such as through interaction with medical devices or by helping healthcare providers to reach medical decisions and communicating with patients, might be treated as devices.⁴ Unfortunately, policing the line of intended use is tricky. There may also be particular concerns about Opensource LLMs, that may be regarded as so-called software of unknown provenance (SOUP) if a third party adapts or uses them as a

component in a medical device, which would trigger special compliance standards and require sufficient documentation that may not always be accessible. Device regulators need to clarify when incorporating an LLM into a medical product renders it a medical device under existing regulations, make fundamental decisions about how to manage adaptive learning in LLMs, and consider how existing risk classification approaches apply to the distinctive setting of LLM use in devices.

Competition Law: Now, at the dawn of medical use of LLMs, one could envision two very different futures. One future is a vibrant ecosystem of medical LLMs trained on different sources with very different designs; the other future is one where two or three very large corporations dominate the LLM market and license their product to all medical users. Each future poses real tradeoffs: can a large number of small firms adequately ensure privacy and other ethics by design? Will consumers be able to adequately distinguish high and low quality LLMs in a crowded market? Will the dominance of a small number of LLM developers result in model homogeneity? Would a small number of developers exert market power in a way that increases prices for patients and health care systems? Antitrust regulators have a key role to play in determining where in between these two futures our world ends up.

Intellectual Property: The competition policy analysis in turn depends on what intellectual property rights (IPRs) we recognize as to LLMs. Recognizing too many IPRs at the (i) computing, (ii) data creation, and (iii) foundation modelling stages of the LLM development could create high barriers to entering the market.⁵ Recognizing too few IPRs, though, may deter some market entrants who cannot raise capital on claims of having an exclusive product at the end of development. The fact that LLMs are often trained on enormous amounts of opaque data sources raises the specter that they themselves may violate existing IPRs. This concern and the lack of transparency as to current LLMs recently resulted in changes to the EU AI Act, which now requires companies deploying generative AI tools to disclose any copyrighted material used to develop their systems.⁶

Cybersecurity and Liability: LLMs may be a force for good and for ill for medical cybersecurity. Generative AI can play a key role in scanning digital logs, finding patterns in vulnerability exploitation, and helping healthcare providers to improve their cybersecurity systems. But security vulnerabilities of LLMs can allow their manipulation and turn them into misinformation sources, generators of more sophisticated and automated fraudulent attacks or spreaders of malware. Hence, minimum security thresholds should be set *before* rolling out LLM applications in healthcare and drug development. For example, foundational open-source AI tools should be based on a foundational programmatic core that effectively reduces the risk of hacks and manipulation. Regulators must also ensure that physicians and other medical staff are well-trained on how LLMs work, their limitations and cybersecurity risks.⁷ Lawmakers must also consider whether they have adequate structures to hold developers accountable and liable for non-compliance with those standards. It will also be important

to clarify when developers can lawfully require that users waive liability claims or indemnify developers from future harms as Open AI, for example, purports to do at the moment.

Regulating all these areas is delicate and only a starting point: as LLMs evolve and become more prominent for medical uses, new risks and benefits will emerge. The challenge is not just in the governance of these technologies but in limits to our current “technologies of governance.” One governance approach is to try to prohibit the use of LLMs in some spheres – in the last several months several countries have announced that they would do so although some have backed off given changes by developers. We are skeptical whether this will be feasible in the long term, both because of political pressure and the ability to circumvent such restrictions. Meanwhile, voices in industry are urging governments to stay out in favor of allowing self-regulation. A different approach is to try to pass new legislation focused on LLMs – the EU’s AI act could serve as a model. The problem is that such legislation risks rigidly bonding medical AI to today’s technical standards which may be inadequate for tomorrow’s problems. We believe that these forms of governance will be important, but so is more open-ended delegation of authority to regulate medical AI to administrative agencies like FDA and EMA as well as common law decision-making by courts, especially as to liability questions.

REFERENCES

1. Moor, M., Banerjee, O., Abad, Z.S.H., et al. Foundation models for generalist medical artificial intelligence. *Nature*. 2023; (616): 259–265.
2. Haupt CE, Marks M. AI-Generated medical advice—GPT and beyond. *JAMA*. 2023; 329(16): 1349–1350.
3. Weatherbed J. OpenAI’s regulatory troubles are only just beginning. *The Verge*. May 5, 2023. <https://www.theverge.com/2023/5/5/23709833/openai-chatgpt-gdpr-ai-regulation-europe-eu-italy>
4. Minssen T, Gerke S, Aboy M, et al. Regulatory responses to medical machine learning. *J. Law & Biosci*. 2020; 7: lsa002.
5. Hoppner T, Streatfeild L. ChatGPT, Bard & Co.: An introduction to AI for competition and regulatory lawyers. *Hausfield Comp. Bull.* 2023. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4371681
6. Mukherjee S, Chee FY, Coulter M. EU proposes new copyright rules for generative AI. *Reuters*. April 28, 2023.
7. Chilton J. The new risks ChatGPT poses to cybersecurity. *Harv. Bus. Rev.* 2023. <https://hbr.org/2023/04/the-new-risks-chatgpt-poses-to-cybersecurity>